

Disperse Dyes derived from 2-Aminoanthraquinone : Synthesis of 2-(2'-Anthraquinonylamino)-4-(*p*-nitrophenylthiourea)-6-methoxy-*s*-triazine Dyes and their Applications

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The literature survey of the disperse dyes based on anthraquinone¹ reveals that these dyes possess good dyeing and fastness properties. Hence, it was thought interesting to undertake the synthesis of disperse dyes based on 2-aminoanthraquinone.

The disperse dyes of the following general structure were synthesised and evaluated their dyeing and fastness properties on polyester fabric.

R = OCH₃, OC₂H₅, OC₃H₇, OC₄H₉, OC₃H₇, OC₄H₉,
2-OCH₃, OC₂H₅, 2-OCH₃, NHC₆H₄, NH.CH₃, NHC₆H₅,

Experimental

p-Nitrophenylthiourea was prepared by reported procedure².

2-(2'-Anthraquinonylamino)-4,6-dichloro-*s*-triazine (A) : 2-Aminoanthraquinone (0.01 mol) was suspended in nitrobenzene (20 ml) and heated to 80°. Cyanuric chloride (0.01 mol) was added to it with stirring and the mixture heated at 115–20° for 4 h. It was then cooled and the resulting solid was washed with petroleum ether and dried.

2-(2'-Anthraquinonylamino)-4-(*p*-nitrophenylthiourea)-6-chloro-*s*-triazine (B) : To a suspension of compound-A (0.01 mol) in acetone (41 ml) was added *p*-nitrophenylthiourea dissolved in acetone was added. The mixture was refluxed at 90° for 3 h, then cooled to room temperature. The resulting solid was washed with petroleum ether and dried.

Reaction of 2-(2'-anthraquinonylamino)-4-(*p*-nitrophenylthiourea)-6-chloro-*s*-triazine (B) with various alcohols and amines : To a suspension of compound-B (0.01 mol) in nitrobenzene (55 ml), excess alcohol or amine was added

and the temperature was raised as indicated in Table 1. The mixture was stirred at 5 h and the resulting yellow products were separated (yields 76–85%).

Application : The materials used and conditions for dyeing of polyester fabric with disperse dyes are as follows : fabric, 2 g; dye, 40 mg; dispersing agent dadamol, 100 mg; MLR, 1 : 50; total volume of dye-bath, 100 ml; pH, 4.0. In order to stabilise the suspension, the suspension stabilising agent are added to the liquor as reported earlier³. High temperature-pressure method was used for dyeing at 120° for 1 h.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF DISPERSE DYES

Dye no.	R-Component	Reaction temp.	M.p. °C	λ_{\max} nm	R_f	Exhaustion %
D-1	Methanol	70–75	263	442	0.44	66
D-2	Ethanol	70–75	247	445	0.53	68
D-3	Propanol	80–90	257	444	0.71	66
D-4	Butanol	80–90	148	443	0.63	67
D-5	2-Methoxyethanol	90–100	238	442	0.39	67
D-6	2-Methoxyaniline	90–100	226	430	0.47	73
D-7	Methylamine	90–100	186	431	0.59	74
D-8	Ethylamine	90–100	207	433	0.81	72
D-9	Dimethylamine	90–100	153	435	0.69	74
D-10	Diethylamine	90–100	286	444	0.68	69
D-11	Morpholine	90–100	257	442	0.54	66
D-12	Piperidine	90–100	284	443	0.59	67

2-(2'-Anthraquinonylamino)-4-(*p*-nitrophenylthiourea)-6-methoxy-*s*-triazine dyes were separated on tlc using chloroform-methanol solvent system : ν_{\max} (KBr) 800 (C₃-N₃), 1 110 (C=S), 1 375–1 460 (CH₃), 1 535 (NH₂), 1 585 (NH₃), 1 670 cm⁻¹ (C=O). The values of λ_{\max} were determined in toluene at 28° using a Bausch and Lomb spectronic-20 spectrophotometer. The general dyebath exhaustion was assessed by spectrophotometric evaluation of the exhaust liquors. The percentage exhaustion of the 2% dyeing on polyester (46–52%) fibre was good to excellent.

Fastness to light, sublimation and acid and alkaine perspiration were assessed by the standard methods of testing (BS : 1006–1978). The rubbing fastness test was carried

out by using a crockmeter (Atlas) in accordance with the AATCC-1961, and the wash fastness, in accordance with IS : 765-1979. The results were found to be moderate to good.

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